

17 - 28 November 2025

AfriPlantSci

ICARDA & UM6P, Morocco

Research skills & modern
breeding techniques for cereals

Schedule

Key: ● Core Skills workshop ● Cultural activity ● Laboratory practical ● Lecture ● Technical workshop

WEEK 1	Sunday (16th)	Monday (17th)	Tuesday (18th)	Wednesday (19th)	Thursday (20th)	Friday (21st)	Saturday (22nd)
09:00-11:00	Arrival to ONOMO Rabat Terminus Hotel for international and UM6P participants and trainers	Welcome, meeting the cohort, and creating your elevator pitch	Gender responsive breeding	Bioflow: an integrated pipeline for quality control and genetic analysis in modern breeding	Effective leadership and management	Refining academic CVs and interview skills	Travel to Ben Guerir and visit to a smallholder cactus farm
11:00-11:30		Coffee break break	Coffee break break	Coffee break break	Coffee break break	Coffee break break	
11:30-12:30		Group activity: sharing science in small groups	How policy works	Continued	Group activity: communicating science to different audiences	Continued	
12:30-13:15		Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	
13:15-15:15		Introduction to the UK-CGIAR Centre project	Panel discussion: sharing policy experiences	Using the Ensembl Plants database	Construct design and assembly	Scientific lecture: Diane Saunders	
		AfriPlantSci 2025 course overview	Scientific lecture: James Karaija	Coffee break	Coffee break	Scientific lecture: Awais Rasheed	
15:15-15:30		Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
15:30-16:30		Introduction to ICARDA and site tour	Building collaborative networks	Further wheat bioinformatics resources	Networking session	Responsible use of AI	
16:30-17:30	Return to accommodation and dinner	Group activity: applying to scientific conferences	Group activity: applying to scientific conferences	Return to accommodation and dinner	Return to accommodation		
17:30-21:00		Return to accommodation and dinner	Return to accommodation and dinner	Networking reception at British ambassador's residence		Return to accommodation and dinner	

WEEK 2	Sunday (23rd)	Monday (24th)	Tuesday (25th)	Wednesday (26th)	Thursday (27th)	Friday (28th)	Saturday (29th)
09:00-11:00	Marrakesh guided tour	Introduction to UM6P and site tour	Pipette handling skills	Assembly of a wheat genome editing construct	Colony PCR	Plasmid purification	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers.
			PCR	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:00-11:30			Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:30-12:30		Lunch	Gel electrophoresis	Scientific lecture: Valentine Otang Ntui	Colony PCR	Sample preparation for plasmid Sanger sequencing	
12:30-13:15			Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	
13:15-14:15		Guide design, transformation, and screening for edits	Scientific lecture: Susanne Dreisigacker	GetGenome presents: don't clone alone, ensure your vectors are verified	Group activity: revision and reflection	Group activity: revision and reflection	
14:15-15:15			Additional genome editing techniques	<i>E. coli</i> transformation	AfriPlantSci 2025 closing ceremony		
15:15-15:30		Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break		
15:30-16:30	Genome editing in wheat: case study on GW2	Analysing Sanger sequencing data with Benchling	GetGenome presents: don't clone alone, ensure your vectors are verified	GetGenome presents: don't clone alone, ensure your vectors are verified	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers		
16:30-20:00	Free time	Free time	Free time	Free time	Onward travel for non-UM6P participants and trainers		
17:30-19:30	Free time	Group activity: critically evaluating scientific papers	Group activity: designing scientific posters and presentations	Free time			
19:30-20:30	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner		

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Participant biographies

Driss Jebli Chrifi holds a Bachelor's degree in Genomics and a Master's degree in Plant Biotechnology for Plant Breeding. He has research experience in molecular biology, plant genomics, and biotechnology through internships at INRA Rabat and Medbiotech. Currently, he is pursuing a PhD in Plant Genome Editing at UM6P, focusing on enhancing tomato traits such as disease resistance, yield, and shelf life. His work combines molecular techniques with bioinformatics to improve crop performance. Beyond research, he enjoys exploring new technologies, learning languages, and sharing knowledge with others in the scientific community.

Ekemeabasi Fidelis Ewona is a PhD candidate at Mohammed VI Polytechnic University (UM6P), Morocco, working at the African Genome Center in the Plant Genome Editing Unit. She holds a BSc in Genetics and Biotechnology and an MSc in Plant Biotechnology. Her current research focuses on using CRISPR-Cas9 gene editing to reduce seed coat hardness in Egusi melon by targeting lignin biosynthesis pathways. Beyond her academic work, she enjoys singing as an expression of gratitude and connecting with people through meaningful conversations. She looks forward to exchanging knowledge and experiences during the training.

El Kendi Fatima Zahra is a PhD student in plant genome editing at AGC-UM6P. She has a strong academic record and hands-on experience in molecular biology and biotechnology which she acquired through her bachelor's and master's in biotechnology. Her research interests focus on plant molecular biology, genetics, and biotechnology, and she is currently working on applying genome editing technologies, mainly CRISPR/Cas9, to improve agricultural traits in both rice and cactus. Outside the lab, she enjoys baking, sewing, artistic activities and working out.

Fatima Zahra Mssilea is a PhD student at ICARDA in Morocco. Her research focuses on identifying resistance sources to Septoria tritici blotch in spring bread wheat. She conducts evaluations at both the adult plant stage in the field and the seedling stage under controlled greenhouse conditions. Her work aims to support breeding strategies for improved disease resistance and sustainable wheat production.

Fatma Omar is a biotechnologist and science communicator from Kenya, currently serving as a Research and Teaching Assistant at the Institute for Biotechnology Research, JKUAT. She holds an MSc in Biotechnology, where her research focused on microbial genomics, plant health, and the resistome pathogens using metagenomic approaches. Her work bridges biotechnology, bioinformatics, and science policy, with a strong commitment to youth and women's empowerment in agriculture. She was named OFAB (Open Forum for Agricultural Biotechnology) Kenya Champion of the Year 2024 for her outstanding advocacy in biotechnology, leading campaigns to combat misinformation and championing inclusive innovation.

Dr Hafssa Kabbaj is a Research associate at ICARDA. She is the genomic selection leader of the durum wheat breeding program at ICARDA Morocco. Her work aims to implement genomic selection and speed breeding tools to deliver super cultivars to national partners from Central and West Asia, North Africa, and West Africa. She holds a PhD in plant breeding and biotechnology from the Faculty of Sciences at Mohammed V University.

Houda Ghait is a Research Assistant in the Plant Gene Editing Laboratory at AGC, Mohammed VI Polytechnic University (UM6P), Morocco. She holds a Master's degree in Bioengineering, with training in molecular biology and biotechnology. Her current research focuses on developing and applying CRISPR-based gene editing tools for crop improvement, she is passionate about innovative plant science approaches that contribute to food security and sustainability. She enjoys reading, traveling, music and spending quality time with her family.

Imane El Ftouh is a PhD student in wheat breeding at the Hassan II Institute of Agronomy and Veterinary Medicine (IAV Hassan II) in collaboration with INRA, Morocco. My research focuses on developing resilient and high-performing wheat varieties through the integration of high-throughput phenotyping, molecular screening (KASP genotyping), and modeling approaches. I am currently conducting multi-location field trials across different agro-ecological zones in Morocco to evaluate wheat performance under drought and salinity stress, combining agronomic, physiological, and socio-economic analyses. My goal is to contribute to sustainable breeding strategies that enhance climate resilience and food security. Beyond research, I enjoy swimming, engaging in social initiatives that support rural communities.

Imane Sarroukh is a PhD candidate at the National Institute of Agronomic Research (INRA), Rabat, Morocco. Her research focuses on the application of CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing in lentil (*Lens culinaris*) to enhance resistance to *Orobanche* spp., devastating parasitic weeds that severely affect legume productivity. She combines molecular genetics, in vitro culture, and plant physiology to optimize regeneration and transformation systems. In addition to her experimental work, she applies data analysis and bioinformatics to study genetic diversity and molecular responses. Her research contributes to the development of sustainable strategies for legume improvement.

Kainat Abbasi is from Islamabad, Pakistan. She has completed an M.Phil. in Plant Sciences from Quaid-i-Azam University, specializing in Plant Molecular Breeding. Her research focused on the molecular characterization of YSL genes in wheat and their role in biofortification. As the eldest in her family, she aspires to be the first to pursue a PhD in Crop Genetics, which motivates her to excel further in this field. Beyond academics, she enjoys travelling and engaging in thoughtful discussions. She is excited to be part of this workshop to learn, collaborate, and apply new techniques.

Participant biographies

Khaoula Lahrichi is a PhD student in wheat genetics and breeding, with a strong focus on developing cultivars resilient to both biotic and abiotic stresses. Her work integrates classical breeding approaches with modern genomic tools to enhance disease resistance, grain quality and climate adaptability in bread wheat. She has hands-on background in making strategic crosses for trait improvement and in managing field and greenhouse trials, aiming to combine favorable traits and broaden the genetic base for resistance. Her research includes genome-wide association studies (GWAS), genomic prediction, and gene expression analysis to identify and validate candidate genes associated with key agronomic and resistance traits.

Manfred Miheso is a plant biotechnologist at the Kenya National Agriculture and Livestock Research Organisation (KALRO). He holds a BSc in Microbiology and Biotechnology and is an MSc in Biotechnology finalist at JKUAT. His work focuses on use of marker-assisted selection to improve crop productivity, managing plant diseases, and supporting sustainable food systems. He has experience in plant diagnostics, molecular biology, and tissue culture. Outside work, he enjoys traveling, swimming, mentoring young scientists, and exploring new technologies that benefit farmers. He is excited to learn from this course and share ideas with fellow participants.

Dr Marwa El-Deriny is a Senior Researcher in Nematology and Biotechnology at the Plant Pathology Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Egypt. She earned her PhD from Mansoura University, where her research focused on the integrated management of plant-parasitic nematodes. Her current work includes molecular identification of nematodes, development of biocontrol strategies for sustainable nematode management. She is involved in several international projects, including those funded by the PRIMA program. She is also passionate about finding sustainable solutions to improve crop health and look forward to exchanging knowledge with her colleagues at the AfriPlantScience.

Nour el houda Safdi is currently a PhD candidate in the Agrobiosciences program at Mohammed VI Polytechnic University (UM6P), Morocco. Her research focuses on plant-insect interactions, particularly the genetic mechanisms underlying cactus resistance to cochineal. She applies omics approaches including genomics, transcriptomics and proteomics to investigate resistance traits and genetic diversity. She also has experience working on metagenomics and crop protection projects. She holds a master's degree in Improvement of Agricultural Production. Outside of research, she enjoys reading, traveling, and exploring new cultures. She looks forward to learning and exchanging ideas with fellow attendees during this course.

Dr Nourhan Fouad is a Senior Research Assistant in the Genetic Innovation/Biotechnology Department at ICARDA, where she has worked since 2014. She earned her BSc in Biotechnology from Cairo University in 2011, and prior to joining ICARDA, she worked at the Agricultural Genetic Engineering Research Institute (AGERI) from 2011 to 2014. Nourhan recently completed her PhD in Biotechnology at Cairo University (2025) and holds a Master's degree from the same institution (2019). Her research focuses on genome editing and molecular biotechnology to improve crop resilience and productivity, particularly in cereals and legumes. She is involved in collaborative CRISPR-based projects for chickpea and barley improvement.

Dr Ola Mossad Mohamed Abd El-Alim holds a PhD in Plant Breeding (2024) with a specialization in wheat improvement under salinity stress, integrating both conventional breeding and biotechnological approaches. She is currently a researcher at the Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Egypt, contributing to projects that aim to enhance crop productivity and resilience. Her academic record includes six published papers and participation in several international conferences and training programs across Egypt, Morocco and Finland. She is married to a fellow researcher in the same field, and together they are raising three sons. Outside of work, she enjoys reading and drawing, which provide balance and inspiration alongside her scientific career.

Dr Sara Fahde, has nurtured a passion for science since her early years. She earned her Bachelor's and Master's degrees in Microbiology, where she developed a strong interest in plant-microorganism interactions. This passion led her to pursue a PhD in Plant Physiology, Microbiology, and Molecular Biology. Her doctoral research explored the molecular identification and effectiveness of *Rhizobium* strains nodulating chickpea to assess their potential as biofertilizers. She has published her findings in several international peer-reviewed journals, adding to the growing body of knowledge on plant-microorganism interactions and their role in sustainable agriculture. Her research provides valuable insights into addressing agricultural challenges related to climate change and food security.

Tadelech Bizuneh Demisse holds both a BSc and MSc in Biotechnology. He joined the Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research (EIAR) in 2016. In 2018, he began an MSc program in Plant Biotechnology at Addis Ababa University (AAU), where he received a graduate fellowship from ILRI in Addis Ababa in 2019 to support his thesis research. After finishing his MSc in 2021, he returned to EIAR as a research assistant. In 2024, he received the CGIAR-UM6P scholarship and enrolled as a doctoral student at the College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (AgBS) at UM6P. His research interests include genetic analysis, gene editing, and gene expression studies, with a focus on using advanced genome editing tools to promote sustainable crop improvement. Currently, his PhD project focuses on potato gene editing for heat stress tolerance.

Youshaa Danyal is from Pakistan and is currently pursuing his third year PhD at the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Beijing, China. His research focuses on QTL mapping and GWAS to identify key genes regulating Zn, Fe, and phytase pathways in wheat. He has also characterized NRAMP, ZIFL, and phosphate transporter families, and completed a wheat blast GWAS project with novel markers soon to be submitted. During his Master's, he conducted a CRISPR-Cas9 project targeting the phytic acid pathway in Zincol-16, and in his Bachelor's, he worked on WRKY genes, graduating with a gold medal. He enjoys cooking in his free time.

Zeineb Dagdad is a third-year PhD student at ICARDA (Morocco) specializing in root phenotyping and the genetic improvement of rotational crops resilient to environmental change. Originally from Guelmim in the Saharan region of Morocco, she holds a Bachelor's degree in Plant Biotechnology from the Faculty of Science and Technology Marrakech, and a Master's degree in Plant Biotechnology and Breeding from the Faculty of Science, Mohammed V University Rabat. Her research began with field screening of olive tree varieties for resistance to Peacock's Eye disease, followed by greenhouse studies on the use of Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia illucens*) frass as a biofertilizer and biocontrol agent in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.).

Dr Zennah Kosgey, from Kenya is a research scientist at Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO)-Food Crops Research Centre. She completed her PhD in Plant pathology from University of Minnesota, USA in 2019 and holds a MSc. in Plant breeding from Kenya. As a research scientist, her current roles includes spearheading disease surveillance work across wheat-growing regions of Kenya, leading the race typing and characterization of stem rust isolates, and performing efficacy tests of new fungicides. As the lead on the Plant Health Initiative (PHI) project in collaboration with CIMMYT, she has played a crucial role in distributing rust resistance monitoring nurseries, contributing to the assessment of virulence diversity and shifts in new virulence. Zennah won the 2024 Women in Triticum (WIT) Early Career Award.

Trainer biographies

Achaimaa Mдини is the Business Partner Communication at the College of Agriculture & Environmental Sciences (CAES) at UM6P, where she expertly navigates the intersection of UM6P's strategic communication and CAES stakeholder engagement. Beginning her journey at UM6P as a Digital & Communication Project Management Officer at the School of Agriculture, Fertilisation & Environmental Sciences, she quickly established herself as a visionary in the field. Prior to her tenure at UM6P in 2022, Achaimaa honed her skills in marketing and communication across the fashion industry - working with prestigious names like NYFW in the US and Galeries Lafayette in France - as well as in the insurance and banking sectors.

Prof. Ahmed Elkot comes from the South Village in Giza (Saqqara) that contains ancient burial grounds of Egyptian royalty, serving as the necropolis for the ancient Egyptian capital, Memphis. He holds a PhD in Biotechnology from the Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), during his PhD he worked on marker assisted transfer of novel powdery mildew resistance genes from the diploid wheat *Triticum boeoticum* to hexaploid bread wheat. He is particularly interested in mapping and transferring disease resistance genes from wild relatives of wheat and exotic materials to cultivated wheat. He is passionate about improving and releasing bread and durum wheat cultivars and support farmers through implementation of the Good Agricultural Practices (GAP).

Angela Payne currently works as a Science Support Administrator at JIC, primarily supporting two of the largest research departments, their groups and members. In addition to this, she has been heavily involved in organising AfriPlantSci 2025. She has over 18 years' experience in administration and project management and holds a BSc Hons in Anthropology. Her background allows her to combine anthropological insights with structured project management skills to support the departments' activities and needs. Angela loves being organised and finding efficiencies which can make life easier for everyone. She thrives from using her expertise to help researchers, by handling tasks that allow them to focus on their core science, and by facilitating collaborations that bring people together.

Dr Anna Backhaus recently joined the IPK institute in Germany as group leader for Resources Genetics & Reproduction (RGR) in the genebank department. In this capacity, she oversees the management and regeneration of IPK's ex situ collection of legume, cereal, vegetable and medicinal plants. Anna earned her PhD from the John Innes Centre, after which join ICARDA (Morocco) as a postdoctoral researcher, working on pre-breeding for cereals with landraces and especially crop wild relatives. At ICARDA, she was also the co-lead of the UK-CGIAR Centre funded project at the heart of this workshop.

Dr Anne Edwards is originally from Wales, UK. She is a research scientist in the Department of Metabolic Biology at the John Innes Centre, and works on the amazing grasspea, *Lathyrus sativus*, a nutritious plant that shows remarkable resilience to extreme climate conditions including drought and flooding. Grasspea also produces ODAP, a neurotoxin. She is studying how and why this toxin is made with the aim of breeding low toxin varieties. She is passionate about all aspects of plant science, but particularly the amazing array of chemicals that plants are able to make. She is also a very keen nature-lover and in her spare time helps to manage an ancient woodland in Norfolk.

Prof. Awais Rasheed is working as a Wheat Breeder at the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT) based in China. He has been affiliated with CIMMYT since 2013 and held different positions related to wheat genomics and breeding. His research areas include wheat molecular breeding, especially developing new genotyping platforms with strong application in wheat breeding. He was recipient of the 2013 Vavilov-Frankel Fellowship from Bioversity International and 2015 recipient of the Excellent Young Scientist from CAAS. He has successfully developed several high-throughput genotyping platforms like KASP assays, SNP chips and genotyping-by-targeted sequencing platforms for use in wheat breeding research.

Prof. Cristóbal Uauy is the director of the John Innes Centre, taking on this role in September 2025. He is internationally recognised for his significant contribution to the development of resources and tools available to the wheat research community which allow for the rapid identification of genes for key traits. His research has identified important genes for improved yield, quality and disease resistance and his lab has developed numerous open-access tools and resources to enhance scientific discovery. As a result of these contributions, Cristóbal has been recognised as a Web of Science Highly Cited Researcher on multiple occasions. He is passionate about the future of plant and microbial science and training the next generation of crop scientists and was recognised in 2021 with the Jeanie Borlaug Women in Triticum (WIT) Mentor Award.

Prof. Diane Saunders OBE is Head of the Crop Genetics department at the JIC, leading research into (re-)emerging plant pathogens that pose a significant threat to agriculture. Diane is well known for her breadth of expertise in plant pathology, which she has applied to study some of the most important plant diseases worldwide, making many notable contributions, as reflected in her award of the highly prestigious RKS Wood Prize by the British Society for Plant Pathology in 2024. These contributions include recent work evaluating re-emergence of wheat stem rust in the UK, developing innovative genomic-led approaches for identification of new sources of wheat rust resistance, and pioneering techniques in pathogen surveillance; the revolutionary "field pathogenomics" and "MARPLE diagnostics" techniques.

Dr Dina Najjar joined ICARDA in 2014 as a social and gender specialist. A socio-cultural anthropologist by training, she focuses on the link between gender equality and policies; agricultural technologies and delivery systems; rural employment and migration; adaption to climate change; and productive assets, including access to land and ownership, in the Middle East and North Africa. Her geographical expertise includes Egypt, Jordan, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, and Sudan. She has also conducted research in Uzbekistan, Kenya, Ethiopia, and India. Dr. Najjar is fluent in Arabic and proficient in French and Swahili. She received her Ph.D. in anthropology from the University of Western Ontario, Canada.

Ella Penny is a 3rd year PhD student at the John Innes Centre. Her research focuses on the development of wheat inflorescence (spike) architecture using computational methods, supervised by Richard Morris and Cristóbal Uauy. She previously studied leaf development in barley during her undergraduate degree at the University of Edinburgh and spent two years working as a data scientist at a medtech startup, developing computer vision methods to analyse human MRI images. Ella is particularly interested in how interdisciplinary approaches can advance fundamental understanding of plant development.

Fatima Zahrae Kharchouch is a Research Program Administrator at ICARDA, where she supports the coordination and management of scientific projects focused on advancing sustainable agriculture in dry regions. Her role bridges administrative excellence and strategic project support – from managing budgets and human resources to ensuring the smooth implementation of research activities across international teams. Beyond program administration, she actively contributes to event organization and stakeholder engagement, helping plan and execute high-level scientific meetings, workshops, and institutional events that connect researchers, partners, and donors.

Dr James Canham is an Entrepreneur-in-Residence at The Sainsbury Laboratory, UK, and co-founder and CEO of GetGenome, a non-profit that supports scientists in accessing genomics technologies and training. He earned his MSci. in Plant Sciences from the University of East Anglia in 2017 and completed his PhD in molecular plant–insect interactions at the John Innes Centre in 2022. Shaped by his experiences in international collaboration, James is committed to advancing equitable access to science. At GetGenome, he leads strategy and operations, combining scientific expertise with organisational leadership to empower researchers worldwide.

Dr James Karanja is a seasoned plant breeder and Chief Research Scientist at KALRO. His work centers on understanding the molecular and physiological pathways that establish plant immunity against pests, diseases, parasitic weeds, and drought. His research has been instrumental in developing resilient maize varieties that support food security and improve the livelihoods of Kenyan farmers. Dr Karanja holds an MSc in Genetics from the University of Nairobi and a PhD in Plant Breeding from the University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. His expertise lies in breeding maize varieties with tolerance or resistance to Maize Lethal Necrosis (MLN), drought, and Fall Armyworm (FAW). Currently, he serves as the Country Coordinator for the TELA/ BMSS Maize Project.

Dr Joe Win is a Senior Research Associate at the Sainsbury Laboratory (TSL) with a wealth of research experience in molecular biology of plant-microbe interactions (Clarivate h-index of 49 and Highly cited researcher 2014-2018). He earned his PhD in Biological Sciences from the Auckland University and did his postdoctoral research at the Ohio State University before joining TSL. He uses genomics, proteomics and other molecular tools to dissect how plant pathogens cause disease on crops and model plants. He has played a critical role in investigating the origin of wheat blast epidemic in Bangladesh and Zambia, and establishing “OpenWheatBlast” web portal for open science initiatives aiming at rapid data release and sharing. He was instrumental in establishing the T-Plex high-throughput genotyping platform at TSL.

Dr Josh Waites is a plant scientist specialising in precise genome editing of polyploid crops like wheat and oilseed rape. He completed his PhD at the John Innes Centre in the UK, where he developed CRISPR/Cas9 and prime editing systems in wheat to enhance carotenoid content. During his postdoctoral fellowship at CIMMYT in Mexico, he led wheat genome editing efforts focused on improving disease resistance, achieving the installation of a rust resistance allele using prime editing. Josh also has experience in developing wheat-compatible vectors through cloning, optimising transformation pipelines and establishing genotyping assays for edited lines. He is now applying Cas12a in oilseed rape at the John Innes Centre. In his spare time he enjoys reading and playing music, especially jamming with other people on his guitar.

Khaled Al-Shamaa is an Associate Scientist in Biometrics at ICARDA. Since joining in 2002, he has conducted more than 75 training courses across 27 countries in the CWANA region. He has contributed to the development of several open-source tools, including the R Shiny framework from Posit, ASRgwas and ASReml-R from VSNi, as well as the ODK Collect and KSU Android Fieldbook mobile applications. In 2012, he was part of the team that received the Khalifa International Date Palm Award for Distinguished Research. Khaled holds a B.Sc. and a diploma in computer engineering from Aleppo University. He also earned certificates in Data Science from Johns Hopkins University and in Statistics for Biosciences from the University of Oxford.

Kestrel Maio is a third year PhD student at the John Innes Centre working under the supervision of Dr Richard Smith on leaf shape development. She uses a combination of molecular and computational tools to characterize the role of boundaries in the outgrowth of the flat, ovate shape of the *Arabidopsis thaliana* leaf. She holds an MSc in Plant Genetics and Crop Improvement, where she studied the advancement of technologies in crop breeding and conducted a 6-month research project investigating symmetry development in the *Arabidopsis thaliana gynoecium*. Outside of academia she enjoys running, hiking, reading, travelling, and knitting.

Maryeme Benounou has a background in plant breeding, with an engineering degree from Institut Agronomique et Vétérinaire Hassan II, Rabat. She recently completed a joint master's degree in Conservation Ecology and Tropical Biodiversity, between France, Malaysia, and Belgium, during which she gained experience in genetic diversity analysis, molecular biology techniques, and bioinformatics. She currently works as a Senior Research Assistant in *Opuntia* breeding at ICARDA-Rabat, with the aim of creating resistant varieties against the cactus cochineal. In her free time, Maryeme enjoys reading, learning languages and hiking.

Dr Matt Heaton is a Research Associate at the Norwich Institute for Sustainable Development and the University of East Anglia. His work spans plant and social sciences, at the interface of agriculture, smallholders and technology. He works on the UK-CGIAR Science Centre on the wheat project studying policy and farmer perceptions around rust resistant, high-iron wheat.

Samuel Shackleton-Chavez, who goes by his middle name Matthew, is currently a PhD student studying CRISPR-Cas9 Gene Drives in the Mediterranean Fruit Fly at the University of East Anglia. Previously, he attended Imperial College London for his Masters which focused on gene editing, as well as his Bachelors in broad Biology and Genetics at Oxford Brookes University. He is most interested in applying CRISPR-Cas9 in different organisms and the many functions this can be used for. Having previously worked on human primary cells and on *Drosophila* to edit visible phenotypes, he enjoys the lab-based elements of building constructs for gene editing and modification. Furthermore, he is interested in teaching in his future career, and is looking forward to being a part of the delivery of this training course.

Dr Maximilian Jones is currently the Project Manager for AfriPlantSci 2025. Before this, Max was a PhD student at the John Innes Centre studying the genetics of inflorescence development in polyploid crops through both bioinformatic and wet lab methods. During this time, Max investigated the genetic networks underlying basal spikelet infertility in wheat and conducted a *k*-mer based GWAS study on *Eragrostis tef*, a staple crop in Ethiopia and Eritrea. He studied Natural Sciences at the University of Cambridge for his undergraduate, followed by a research technician position focused on monocotyledon grafting. Outside of work, Max enjoys rock climbing, reading, and wild plant identification.

Dr Nikolai Adamski is a wheat geneticist working at the John Innes Centre in Norwich. His work focuses on understanding the genetic programs controlling the development of the wheat inflorescence. To achieve this, Nikolai is using genetic and genomic approaches to study variation in spikelet and floret size and shape within a diverse set of germplasm, including landraces, wheat subspecies, and mutant populations. Nikolai is passionate about training (early career) scientists in using the multitude of available wheat genomics tools for their research. He has participated in several training workshops within the UK and abroad.

Dr Samar Naseer is a lecturer in Biology at Allama Iqbal Open University, Islamabad, Pakistan. Her research focuses on wheat biofortification to enhance grain iron and zinc content. During her PhD, she utilized CRISPR/Cas9-based gene editing in two wheat varieties to improve grain iron levels. In addition, she conducted transcriptome profiling of the high-zinc wheat variety Zincol-2016 to investigate the genetic basis of its elevated zinc trait. She is passionate about advancing scientific innovation in wheat research and contributing to global food and nutritional security.

Prof. Shireen Abdel-Halim Assem is a Full Professor of Plant Biotechnology and Molecular Biology at ARC. She was the former Vice President of ARC for Research Affairs (2018-July 2025), and former Director of the Agricultural Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering Research Institute (AGERI) at ARC. Shireen is a Fulbright alumna through a postdoctoral research grant in the USA. She has led several national and international basic and applied research projects on different applications of biotechnology such as molecular breeding, genetic engineering and genome editing and she has several publications in peer reviewed journals. Her latest scientific achievement is applying the genome editing technology CRISPR/Cas-9 to develop cereal crops with improved traits for climate resilience.

Dr Susanne Dreisigacker is leading the Wheat Molecular Breeding Laboratory and pre-breeding activities at the International Wheat and Maize Improvement Center (CIMMYT) in Mexico. Dr Dreisigackers' main interest is to bring promising genomics tools into use in the CIMMYT Global Wheat Program. Her lab conducts genetics studies on key biotic, abiotic and quality factors that limit the production and value of wheat especially in the developing world. She provides the Global Wheat Program access to state-of-the-art molecular tools and together with the CIMMYTs wheat breeders she applies genomics-assisted selection strategies such as MAS, MABC and genomic selection targeting to accelerate genetic gains in bread and durum wheat.

Prof. Valentine Otang Ntui is a Professor of Plant Genome Editing at the African Genome Center, Mohammed VI Polytechnic University (UM6P), Morocco, and a Professor of Plant Biotechnology at the University of Calabar, Nigeria. His research focuses on improving agricultural crops using omics, molecular biology, genetic engineering, and genome editing tools to enhance agronomic and nutritional traits. He earned his Ph.D. in Plant Biotechnology from Chiba University, Japan, and completed postdoctoral fellowships at Chiba University and King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Saudi Arabia. Formerly a Scientist at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Kenya, Dr. Ntui has trained numerous African scientists in CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing and supervised several graduate students.

Welcome, meeting the cohort, and developing elevator pitches

Trainers: Prof. Diane Saunders & Eleanor Penny (JIC)

This first session provides an informal introduction to the course and to each other. The session will open with a welcome from Prof. Diane Saunders, one of the research leads on the UK-CGIAR Centre project underlying AfriPlantSci 2025. We will then have a few icebreaker activities, giving you a chance to meet one another and connect within the group. We will then turn to developing effective elevator pitches, so that you can develop your own memorable introductions to yourselves and your work. By the end of the session, you will have met and connected within the cohort, and begun to develop a personalised pitch of yourself and your work.

What is an elevator pitch?

As scientists, we are often asked about our work. This requires us to communicate in a concise and compelling way. Imagine you enter an elevator with someone you've been dying to meet. As you ride up to your floor, you have 30 seconds to connect and make an impression. This is an elevator pitch.

This session will help you develop your own elevator pitch to memorably convey who you are, what you do, and why it matters. It can be used in any setting, including both scientific and non-specialist but influential audiences. They are also a great way to start a memorable written application for a grant or job. We will go through some exercises to help develop your elevator pitch and throughout the next two weeks there will be many opportunities allowing you to practise and hone yours.

Remember, we can tailor these to specific audiences, but they do not need to be technical! These are an invitation for further conversation, rather than the opportunity to tell everything you can in 30 seconds.

Exercises:

The following four questions will provide content ideas for your elevator pitch. Give them some thought and be ready to discuss your answers in the session.

Who are you and where do you work?

What do you do and what research questions are you trying to address?

What have you contributed to addressing these research questions?

What impact will a successful outcome have on your wider field?

To be completed during the session:

What do you want your listener to take away?

What makes you and your work memorable?

What would you like people to remember about you after that initial introduction?

Group activity: sharing science in small groups

Trainer: Ella Penny (JIC)

Being a scientist is not only about generating knowledge, but also about communicating it effectively and building collaborations. The ability to clearly discuss your research allows you to connect with your peers, build collaborations, and generate interdisciplinary ideas.

In the previous session, we developed our elevator pitches. This is an opportunity to practise and hone these, and to dig a little deeper into each others' work. In small groups, you will discuss your science and find similarities and differences between your research and skillsets. The aim of this session is to learn about each other's research and motivation, and to practise framing your science in a way that builds connections with fellow researchers.

Discussion points

- » What questions in science are you currently excited by?
- » What are the main tools and methods that you use day to day?
- » Are there any techniques you are curious to know about?
- » Does your work include field, lab, or computational work?
- » What do you enjoy most about your work?
- » What do you find the most challenging about your work?
- » Do you have any collaborations?

UK-CGIAR Centre project: leveraging genetic innovations for accelerated breeding of climate resilient and nutritious crops

Speaker: Prof. Diane Saunders OBE (JIC)

The UK-CGIAR Centre for Collaboration in Science and Innovation, funded by the Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO) of the UK Government, aims to support global food security by bringing together scientists from the UK, CGIAR, and countries where research will be applied to form impact-focused research collaborations. Countries in the Global South with low domestic agricultural productivity, low food security and a requirement to import staples are at risk. The improvement of food staples through breeding provides an excellent route to increase agricultural productivity and food/nutrition security, especially in systems where the use of chemical inputs such as fertilizers or pesticides is limited by affordability and access. However, traditional breeding methods are slow in the context of current global crises and often incremental, delivering too little advantage to the farmer to encourage adoption.

This project aims to address the above challenge by accelerating the breeding process and delivering higher genetic gain by adopting new breeding approaches (genome editing), exploiting novel genetic variation, and developing data-driven approaches. This is being delivered through collaboration between ICARDA, CIMMYT, Kenya Agriculture and Livestock Research Organisation, Agricultural Research Centre Egypt, Quaid-I-Azam University, John Innes Centre, and Norwich Institute for Sustainable Development. This project is addressing the following specific research questions: **(i)** Can genome editing of susceptibility factors provide a durable source of wheat rust resistance?, **(ii)** Can genome editing significantly increase iron levels in wheat flour? and **(iii)** Can whole genome sequence data be effectively used to accelerate trait discovery and deployment in crop breeding programmes? This project also integrates CGIAR and NARES breeding efforts, strengthening NARES capacity to utilize these new breeding strategies.

9:00 - 11:00 Tuesday | Session 6 | Technical skills

Gender responsive breeding

Trainer: Dr Dina Najjar (ICARDA)

This training introduces participants to the foundations of gender analysis and its critical role in agricultural research and development, with a particular focus on plant breeding and related projects. Drawing on empirical evidence and case studies, the course highlights how gender shapes access to resources, decision-making, technology adoption, and productivity. Participants will learn why neglecting gender considerations leads to incomplete analyses and missed opportunities for impact, while integrating gender can enhance yields, increase incomes, and reduce food insecurity. The sessions will cover key concepts, methods for collecting and using sex-disaggregated data, and strategies to design gender-responsive interventions across the project cycle. Practical exercises and group discussions will equip participants to identify bottlenecks, challenge stereotypes, and propose transformative solutions. By linking theory to practice, the training aims to build capacity for mainstreaming gender in research, policy, and development initiatives that benefit both women and men farmers.

How (public) policy works

Trainer: Matt Heaton (NISD)

The success or failure of attempts to modernise the breeding of cereals globally will rely on a favourable and enabling policy environment. This session explains public policy as an introduction to subsequent dedicated discussion sessions on the policy surrounding novel breeding techniques.

This session will explain the meaning of “policy” as it relates to government intent and describe in outline the policy development process. It will explore the various actors in policy making and, in particular, examine the role of evidence and of scientists in policy. To link this theory to practice, the session will first look at an unrelated (UK) example of policymaking and then invite participants to work in groups to start to think about how policy might impact their own research activity and ambitions.

Participants should leave this session with enough understanding of public policy to enable the framing of any subsequent engagement with the political or policy process.

13:15 - 14:15 Tuesday | Session 8 | Technical skills

Panel discussion: sharing policy experiences

Facilitator: Matt Heaton (NISD)

This panel convenes researchers with substantive experience operating at the interface of bioscience, regulatory science and government across diverse national contexts. Through moderated conversation and audience Q&A, speakers will dissect how scientists can contribute credibly and constructively to policy formulation and implementation, especially in fast-moving areas such as biotechnology and agricultural innovation.

Drawing on examples, the panel will outline share approaches for effective dialogue with ministries and regulators; translating complex evidence into policy-ready narratives; managing uncertainty, risk and values; and navigating institutional constraints, timelines and political windows. Panellists will also reflect on any examples they might have encountered of events that hindered uptake, how scientific advice was sidelined, and what could be done differently (e.g., stakeholder mapping, coalition-building, pre-briefs, and framing around public goods). The session will surface cross-country contrasts and common principles, highlighting ethics, transparency, and equitable participation of affected communities. Early-career researchers will leave with ideas for engagement with policymakers, and a clearer understanding of how to position themselves as trusted expert interlocutors between the laboratory, the regulatory arena and the public interest.

Building collaborative networks

Trainer: Dr Anna Backhaus (IPK, ICARDA)

Successful collaborations are at the heart of impactful research. Whether working across disciplines, institutions, or countries, the ability to manage a collaborative project effectively is an essential skill for researchers at all career stages. While collaborations can bring great ideas and expanded expertise, they also require clear communication, mutual trust, and careful coordination to succeed. In this training module, we will explore strategies for initiating, maintaining, and navigating collaborative partnerships by going through our own experiences so far. Give some thought to the questions below and be ready to discuss them.

Who have you or are you currently collaborating with? How international are your collaborations? Draw your connections on the world map below.

What do you think makes a collaboration successful?

Can you identify potential challenges in managing collaborative work?

Have you had experience of a collaboration that worked particularly well (or not)? What made the difference?

Group activity: applying to scientific conferences

Trainer: Kes Maio (JIC)

This workshop will use peer-assisted methods to explore two key steps in the scientific conference application process: writing a strong abstract and preparing a competitive travel grant application. A well-written abstract is vital to secure a place at the conference, and to inform colleagues in the field what your interests are and your current research area. This could allow for potential collaborators to seek you out during the course of, or sometimes even before, the conference. This workshop will cover what makes an abstract clear, concise, and compelling, and use peer feedback to review examples.

Travel grants provide crucial financial support while also adding recognition and prestige to your CV and future applications. This workshop will explore how to tailor applications to specific awards, highlight your research and background effectively, and ensure your application meets eligibility criteria. Practical exercises and collaborative feedback will offer strategies to optimise both abstracts and grant applications, boosting chances of success at any potential future conference.

Bioflow: an integrated pipeline for quality control and genetic analysis in modern breeding

Trainer: Khaled Al-Shamaa (ICARDA)

This 2-hour online session introduces Bioflow, the CGIAR open-source breeding analytics pipeline designed to implement standardized quality control and quantitative genetic analyses across diverse crop breeding programs. Participants will gain a hands-on understanding of how Bioflow streamlines the integration of phenotypic and genotypic data, ensuring high-quality datasets ready for downstream applications such as GWAS and genomic prediction. The session will highlight how Bioflow produces consistent, reproducible results aligned with the CGIAR Breeding Analytics team's guidelines, recommendations, and best practices. By the end of the session, attendees will understand how Bioflow supports efficient and reliable data analysis workflows, enhancing decision-making in breeding programs and bridging the gap between raw datasets and actionable genetic insights.

Using the Ensembl Plants database

Trainer: Prof. Cristobal Uauy (JIC)

Over the last decade, big data has become ubiquitous in the plant sciences, largely driven by low sequencing costs and other technological advancements. University curriculums, however, are only slowly adapting to these changes, meaning that many plant scientists lack the skills to access and meaningfully interact with all available data. Another major challenge is the fractured nature of the data landscape; a lot of data exists within a multitude of separate domains/databases. There are, however, coordinated efforts to consolidate data where possible into larger, unifying databases. (This is a huge task given the amount of existing data!)

Here, we will introduce the Ensembl Plants database as a convenient and easy-to-use data repository (Yates et al., 2022). All data hosted there is public, meaning there are no restrictions on who can access,

use, and share that data (including you, the user). The database is curated, continually developed, and updated to ensure it is relevant and useful to users. Data can be queried one-by-one or downloaded in bulk using the integrated BioMart tool (Kinsella et al., 2011). BioMart can also be accessed using the R programming language for larger-scale analyses.

A major feature of the website is the ability for cross-species comparative analyses thanks to the Compara gene trees integrated into the database; these gene trees help identify orthologous genes from other species, facilitating comparative analyses - for example, between wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and rice (*Oryza sativa*).

In summary, the Ensembl Plants database is an annotated data repository for many plant species and a highly useful tool for plant science.

Discussion points

Please have a think about these questions ahead of the workshop.
Have you used an online database before? If so, which one and what was your experience with it?

What type of data / features do you use in your day-to-day work?

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Further wheat bioinformatics resources

Trainer: Prof. Cristobal Uauy (JIC)

In the previous session, we introduced the Ensembl Plants database to you. There are also many other, complementary public databases, which we will briefly cover in this session.

Gene expression patterns are crucial for understanding a gene's function. Low sequencing costs have led to a plethora of transcriptome datasets. The expVIP database (<https://www.wheat-expression.com/>) has analysed dozens of publicly available transcriptome studies to create a gene expression atlas for wheat (Borrill, Ramirez-Gonzalez, and Uauy 2016; Ramirez-Gonzalez et al., 2018). In another effort, the transcriptome of a single spring wheat cultivar (Azhurnaya) was assessed in different tissues at different developmental timepoints (https://bar.utoronto.ca/efp_wheat/cgi-bin/efpWeb.cgi) and presented in an easy-to-understand visual format (Ramirez-Gonzalez et al., 2018; Winter et al., 2007).

Apart from bulk tissue expression data, there exists now a spatial transcriptomics dataset for a small gene panel (200 genes) focused on the developing wheat inflorescence (<https://www.wheat-spatial.com/>; Long et al., 2024).

The GrainGenes database (<https://graingenes.org/GG3/>) is similar to Ensembl Plants, but is focused entirely on cereals (Yao et al., 2022). It also contains genetic maps and marker data as well as a list of protocols for various molecular biology techniques.

For barley, similar databases exist to the ones presented for wheat. Most notably, the barley pangenome database (<https://panbarlex.ipk-gatersleben.de/>) contains data for 76 accessions of domesticated and wild barley (Jayakodi et al., 2024). A spatial transcriptomics atlas has also been created for barley (<http://purl.org/barvista/home>; Demesa-Arevalo et al., 2025). Equivalent resources exist for many other plants within both monocots and dicots.

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Effective project management & leadership under time constraints

Trainers: Diane Saunders (JIC)

Effectively managing and leading research projects is a key skill for any Principal Investigator (PI), but often new PI's receive limited training to help them adapt to these new roles. Understanding how to balance the distinct roles of leadership and management of projects when working with your team is key to ensuring project success. But this can be challenging when dealing with the many unexpected constraints and opportunities that arise during project progression. In this training module we will explore core principles of effective project management and leadership and how to effectively lead a project to completion, whilst navigating time constraints.

Exercises

tGive some thought to the questions below and be ready to discuss them.

What do you understand by the terms 'management' and 'leadership'?

What are the qualities of good leadership?

How do you think ineffective time management could influence leadership styles?

Do you struggle with time management? Does this influence your research progress?

Group activity: communicating science to different audiences

Trainer: Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)

In this session we shall learn and practice how to communicate science to different scientific and non-scientific audiences. This is an important skill because as scientists it is our responsibility to ensure our work is known and understood, to ensure we maintain trust in science, funding for future research, and highlight the importance of our work for the future of humanity. We will first overview what kind of audiences we may encounter in our careers, and then role play scenarios to explain different scientific concepts to different audiences, such as politicians, school children, and business investors.

13:15 - 15:15 Thursday | Session 17 | Technical skills

Construct design and assembly

Trainer: Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)

A fundamental component of molecular biology and genome editing is the assembly and use of 'constructs', by which we mean engineered plasmids (rings of dsDNA). Constructs are modified to encode specific functions we would like to use for experimental purposes. In this lecture, we will cover the fundamentals of what a plasmid is, examples of the components used in existing plasmids, and the design of a plasmid we will assemble together in the second week of the course.

This will be followed by an in-depth explanation of how we build plasmids. We will focus on the Golden Gate method, which combines restriction digestion and ligation into a one-pot reaction, but will also touch on the Gibson assembly method. This session will also contain an interactive component, in which we will visually explore how to assemble constructs using overhangs or 'sticky ends' with complementary sequences. By the end of the session we hope to have given you an overview of how constructs are assembled and the key components they encode - including those relating to CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing.

9:00 - 12:30 Friday | Session 18 | Technical skills

Refining academic CVs and interview skills

Trainer: Prof. Diane Saunders OBE (JIC)

This interactive workshop is designed to equip you with the practical tools and confidence needed to present yourself convincingly in the competitive academic job market. Led by Prof. Diane Saunders, creator of the Rosalind Franklin Women in Wheat Champions programme, this session will help you craft an effective academic CV and perform successfully in interviews.

Participants will learn how to structure their CVs to highlight research achievements, publications, teaching experience, and transferable skills in ways that resonate with selection panels. Common pitfalls and misconceptions will be discussed, alongside strategies for tailoring CVs to different types of positions. The workshop will also explore interview preparation, including anticipating typical and challenging questions, communicating research impact, and demonstrating abilities for independence and collaboration. Through a combination of short presentations, group discussions, and practical exercises, attendees will gain insights into what interviewers look for and how to convey their strengths with clarity and authenticity.

By the end of the session, participants will have developed a clearer sense of how to position themselves strategically for the next stage of their careers and will leave with guidance and resources to refine their CVs and interview techniques.

Exercises

Please bring along a printed copy of your current CV to this workshop. This will allow you to analyse each other's CVs in a friendly environment and receive constructive feedback from your peers and the instructors.

13:15 - 14:15 Friday | Session 19 | Scientific lecture

Safeguarding wheat yields from cereal fungal invaders

Speaker by: Prof. Diane Saunders OBE (JIC)

Wheat rusts are known as the "polio of agriculture" due to the threat they pose to wheat production worldwide. Despite long-standing efforts to wrestle the wheat rusts into submission, new strains are constantly evolving that overcome barriers we create to inhibit infection. To tackle these re-emergent threats, our lab uses an integrated genomics-based approach to enhance resilience of our wheat production system. For instance, our "field pathogenomics" strategy, that uses transcriptome sequencing of infected wheat leaves taken directly from the field, has enabled us to gain insight into the wheat rust population structure and monitor emergence of new strains. Using this approach, we also gather insight into plant genes highly expressed during infection that may have functions supporting pathogen colonisation. Disrupting several of these genes has shown their function is essential for supporting wheat rust infection, presenting new targets for manipulation in wheat rust resistance breeding. Furthermore, we also recently developed an award-winning Mobile And Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) diagnostics platform, reducing the speed of strain-level diagnostics from many months using traditional approaches to just 48 hours. Integration of this new methodology into national surveillance programmes is revolutionising the speed of plant disease diagnostics, ensuring timely deployment of intervention strategies.

14:15 - 15:15 Friday | Session 20 | Scientific lecture

Translational genomics for wheat breeding

Speaker: Prof. Awais Rasheed (CIMMYT, QAU)

The completion of the first reference genome sequence of bread wheat (IWGSC, 2018) was a major leap forward for the wheat scientific community. It was difficult to foresee at that time that within the span of a few years, extensive genome sequencing resources of wheat and its wild relatives around the world would be available. We have outlined at least 26 studies that have characterized large wheat populations at a whole-genome level to answer questions related to wheat evolution, domestication, adaptability, wild introgressions, and breeding (Rasheed et al 2025). Such an advancement in wheat genomics over the past 6 years is unparalleled in any other crop species with a giant genome size such as wheat's. However, the efforts to translate this knowledge for practical crop breeding is slow. In this lecture, I discuss the key barriers and possible solutions to overcome these barriers and design genomics-enabled tools and resources for practical wheat breeding.

Responsible use of AI

Trainer: Ella Penny (JIC)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) - typically large language models (LLMs) - is becoming a more frequent player in our lives. Whether it be for social media or published research, we have a responsibility to use AI in the right way, and learn how to spot and critically analyse potentially incorrect information. There are now also clear policies from journals on the use of AI in published work. During this session, we will discuss generative AI and AI-assisted tools, how they can be used and misused, and tips and tricks for responsible interaction with tools and their outputs during our research.

Give some thought to the questions below and be ready to discuss them.

Do you use AI in your work? Which tools?

Think of a time or times you noticed that AI had been used in something you read or saw. How could you tell it had been used?

9:00 - 16:30 | Session 22 | Cultural activity

Visit to a smallholder cactus farm

Led by: Maryeme Benounou (ICARDA)

As we travel from Rabat to Ben Guerir to begin the second week of the course at UM6P, we will stop off at a smallholder cactus farm near a small village called Dar Homad. The farmer, Ahmed, will provide us with a tour of the farm and explain the day-to-day life of a smallholder farmer in this arid region, focusing on *Opuntia* cactus (also called prickly pear). We will hear about this crop's uses, its merits and challenges, and its primary pest, the cochineal beetle. Maryeme is currently working on *Opuntia* speed-breeding at ICARDA Rabat and will provide additional insights into the work being done to improve this important crop.

Guide design, transformation, and screening for edits

Led by: Dr Joshua Waites (JIC)

In week 1 we heard from Matthew Shackleton-Chavez about the design and assembly of genome editing constructs. A key element of this process was the integration of one or more guide RNA (gRNA) sequences for targeting of the Cas9 protein. How, though, do we create effective gRNAs? In this session, Dr Joshua Waites will introduce key concepts underlying guide design for cereals, including length, G/C content, proximity to a protospacer adjacent motif (PAM), and evaluation of candidate sequences for off-target effects. Throughout the remainder of the week, we will perform various laboratory protocols to assemble and validate our own genome editing constructs based on the principles discussed in Matthew and Joshua's workshops.

Once a construct is successfully assembled, it must be transformed into the target germplasm, regenerated, and then screened for edits. In the second half of this session, we will cover each of these downstream steps, highlighting tips and tricks used by researchers at the John Innes Centre and CIMMYT to raise their efficiency and efficacy. Lastly, if the material is to be deployed in field trials or commercially, it is also important to fully segregate out the original construct to ensure the plant counts as a precision-bred organism (PBO) rather than a genetically modified organism (GMO). Guidance for effectively testing this in plants has recently been published:

Huguet-Tapia, J.C., Loo, E.P.I., Buchholzer, M. et al. Ensuring effective removal of transgenes before release of genome-edited crops. *Nat Biotechnol* 43, 1603–1605 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-025-02805-7>

15:30-16:30 Monday | Session 25 | Technical skills

Genome-editing in wheat: a case study using GW2

Trainer: Dr Nikolai Adamski (JIC)

Grain yield is an important agronomic trait and thus a key breeding target, but it is also complex and highly polygenic, especially within a polyploid crop like wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). Brinton and Uauy (2019) argued for a reductionist approach to begin tackling this complexity: they suggested that we need to mechanistically understand how genes affect yield components and then use this knowledge to combine favourable alleles to maximize yield gains while at the same time minimizing negative yield correlations. One important yield component is grain weight, which can in turn be divided into sub-components such as carpel size, grain size, and protein content.

A gene affecting grain weight was cloned in rice (*Oryza sativa*) and named Grain Weight 2 (GW2; Song et al., 2007). The orthologous gene in wheat, TaGW2, was later shown to also affect grain weight by increasing carpel size (Simmonds et al., 2016). This study was conducted using 'Target Induced Local Lesions In Genome' (TILLING) mutants. Unlike rice, where a deleterious mutation of OsGW2 led to an increase of ~50% in grain weight and ~25% increase in grain width, individual mutations within polyploid wheat have smaller effects; on average, single knockout mutations in wheat led to an increase of ~7% in grain weight and ~3% increase in grain width (Wang et al., 2018). These effects were shown to be additive, with a complete knockout of all three copies of TaGW2 causing an increase of ~21% in grain weight and ~9% increase in grain width.

The TILLING mutants contain many background mutations and are limited to two wheat cultivars. Inducing targeted mutations using the CRISPR-Cas9 genome-editing system offers the chance for "clean" edits in a relevant (locally adapted) wheat variety. Guide sequences were designed using the WheatCrispr tool (<https://crispr.bioinfo.nrc.ca/>; Cram et al., 2019).

Exercises

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ATGGGGAACAGAATAGGAGGGAGGAGGAAGGCCGGGGTGGAGGAGCGGTACACGAGGCCGCA
GGGGCTGTACGAGCACAGGGATATCGACCAGAAGAAGCTACGCAAGTTGATCCTCGAGGGCCA
AGCTCGCGCCCTGCTACCCGGGGCTGACGACGCCCGGGGGGTGACCTGGAGGAGTGCCCC
ATCTGCTTCCTGTACTACCCAAGCCTTAACCGATCAAAATGTTGCTCGAAAGGGATATGTAC
AGAGTGCTTTCTTCAAATGAAACCAACTCATACTGCTCGACCTACACAATGCCATTCTGCA
AAACCCCAACTATGCTGTGGAGTATCGTGGTGTAAAGACAAAGGAGGAAAGGAGCATAGAG
CAATTTGAAGAACAGAAAGTCATTGAAGCACAGATGAGGGTGCGGCAGCAAGCACTTCAAGA
CGAAGAGGATAAGATGAAAAGAAAACAGAGTAGGTGCTCTTCTAGCAGAACAATCGTCCAA
CAACAGAAGTGGAGTATCGAGATATTTGCAGCACATCCTATTGAGTCCATCGTACCAATGT
ACCCAGCAAGAACTGAATGTTGTTGCTGCTGAGCCTTCATGTTCTGCTCAGGCTAACATGCC
GTCTTTCCATTCTAGGCATACTCGTGATGATAACATAGACATGAACATAGAGGACATGATGG
TTATGGAAGCGATTGCGGTTCAATTCAGGAGCAAGGAAGTATAGGAAATCCTTCTTGTTGGG
AGCTTTATGCCTTTTGAGCAACCAACCGGTGAGAGGCAGGCATTCGTTGCAGCTCCTCCTCT
AGAAATGCCCATCCTGGTGGATTTCTTGTGCTGTTGCTGCTATGGCTGAGCACCAGCCAT
CAAGCATGGATTTCTCTTACATGACTGGTAGTAGTGCCTTCCAGTCTTTGACATGTTCCGC
CGACCGTGCAACATGCTGGTGGAAAGCATGGGTGCTGCGGAAAGTTCACCAGATAGCTGGAG
CGGGATAGCGCCAAGTTGCAGCAGAAGGGAAGTGGTAAGAGAGGAAGGAGAGTGCTCAACCG
ACCACTTGTGAGAGGGTGCAGAGGCCGGGACAAGCTATGCCGGCTCGGACATTGTGGTGGAT
GCGGGGACAATGCTACCGTTGCCTTTTGTGCTGACAATTACAGTATGGTTGCAAGCCATTTCCG
TCCTGAGAGCATCGAAGAACAATGATGTATTCATGGCTGTTTCTTTAGCAGAAGCTCATG
GTAGAACGCACACGCAAGGGTTGGCATGGTTGTAA
  
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Fig. 1: The wildtype coding sequence of the A-genome copy of GW2 (TraesCS6A02G189300) from wheat accession 'Chinese Spring'. The exons are highlighted in different colours, introns are omitted. START and STOP codons are highlighted in blue with red font. PAM sites are highlighted in black with white font. Guide sequences are in bold font. These guides are compatible across all three copies of GW2. We will be working with the first (i.e. 5'-most) of these guides in the lab later in the week.

Discussion points:

Based on Figure 1:

- What type of edits can you expect to recover within GW2-A1 from this design?
- What would you expect the phenotype of homozygous knockouts to be?

References

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Group activity: critically evaluating scientific papers

Trainer: Kes Maio (JIC)

From undergraduate to seasoned professors, reading academic papers is a skill that needs to be actively maintained and honed at all levels in scientific research. Even for anyone well-practiced in reading research papers, it is important to refresh and reflect on your active reading strategies to optimize your approach. This workshop will use peer-assisted learning and discussion to critically evaluate an academic article and assess how effective it is at delivering its take-home message. Active-reading strategies will be suggested, which will make it easier to keep-up with a rapidly evolving research field. Critical evaluation of a research article will also be emphasized as it is important to remember that what is published is not truth written in stone. The data can be limited itself, and the interpretation might be unsubstantiated by the data presented. It is necessary to bear this in mind throughout the reading of academic papers to prevent the propagation of misinformation. Overall, it is important to remember to be critical but also kind in your assessment. Minor problems, such as spelling errors or mislabelled figure-legends are not as problematic as misrepresenting data. Being aware of your own bias as well as that of the authors can help you make a more fastidious assessment of the paper. An open access paper which may help in evaluating papers going forward is 'Ten simple rules for reading a scientific paper' by Maureen A. Carey, Kevin L. Steiner, and William A. Petri Jr on PLOS computational biology.

Despite the importance of keeping up-to-date with research articles, it can sometimes fall to the wayside as there are other, more urgent demands on time. The workshop will aim to help save hours of work in the lab by providing faster, more efficient strategies of reading and interpreting research articles. In keeping with the themes of the lab-based practicals and the genome editing theory workshops, the paper discussed in this workshop will be:

Wang, W., Pan, Q., He, F., Akhunova, A., Chao, S., Trick, H. and Akhunov, E., 2018. Transgenerational CRISPR-Cas9 activity facilitates multiplex gene editing in allopolyploid wheat. *The CRISPR journal*, 1(1), pp.65-74.

The article can be accessed for free here:
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6319321/>

Workbook content

The questions below are to be completed during the workshop

Before starting to read an academic paper there are some key questions that need to be addressed. Firstly, why are you reading this paper? Is it because you are entering a new field and you would like to find out more about the ongoing research? In this case it is important to focus on the introduction and the discussion parts of the paper. If you are trying to understand a technique better, it may be most useful to read the methods and results sections. If this is a key paper to your area of interest, or you are asked to review an article, the questions below can be applied in your assessment of each of the figures in the results section. Try applying them to one of the figures from Wang et al. 2018.

1. What does the author want to know?

2. What did they do? What was their approach or the methods used?

3. Why was it done in this way?

4. What do the results show?

5. How did the authors interpret the results?

6. What should be done next?

These same questions can also be applied to the whole paper once you have a deeper understanding of the results described by the authors.

1. What does the author want to know?

2. What did they do? What was their approach or the methods used?

3. Why was it done in this way?

4. What do the results show?

5. How did the authors interpret the results?

6. What should be done next?

9:00 - 10:00 Tuesday | Session 27 | Laboratory practical

Pipette handling skills

Trainers: Dr Anne Edwards, Dr Nikolai Adamski, Dr Joshua Waites (JIC)

Accurate use of micropipettes is a fundamental skill in any molecular biology laboratory, as nearly every protocol relies on precise measurement and transfer of small volumes of liquid. This exercise introduces participants to the correct handling and operation of a 2-20 μL micropipette, focusing on setting volumes and maintaining proper pipetting technique.

Micropipetting exercise (2-20 μL micropipette)

Materials

- Micropipette and tip
- Loading buffer
- Parafilm square

WARNING: Do not attempt to adjust the micropipette outside its stated range (below 2 μL or above 20 μL)

HOW TO USE A GILSON MICROPIPETTE

How do I read the volume?
The volume is displayed as three digits which read from top to bottom. The numbers in red on the P20 represent tenths of microlitres (μl).

P20	P200	P1000
1	1	0
2	2	7
5	5	5
12.5 μL	125 μL	0.75 mL

1. Hold the pipette in a vertical position. Push the button smoothly to the first stop position.
2. Put the pipette tip into the liquid. Allow the plunger to move up smoothly to the rest position. Wait one second so that all the liquid has time to move up into the tip.
3. Put the pipette tip into the microtube. Press the push button smoothly as far as it will go and the liquid will be dispensed. Then take the pipette out of the microtube and allow the push button to return to the rest position.

Method

1. Set the micropipette to 10 μL
2. Place two separate 10 μL drops onto the piece of parafilm (A and B)
3. Set the micropipette to 5 μL and take 5 μL from drop A to form another drop C
4. Set the micropipette to 7.5 μL and transfer 7.5 μL from drop B to drop C
5. Set the micropipette to 2.5 μL and transfer 2.5 μL from drop A to drop B and 2.5 μL from drop A to drop C (there should be no liquid left in drop A)
6. Set the micropipette to 5 μL and check that there are 5 μL in drop B; then set it to 15 μL and check that there are 15 μL in drop C.

10:00 - 11:00 Tuesday | Session 28 | Laboratory practical

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR)

Trainers: Dr Anne Edwards, Dr Nikolai Adamski, Dr Joshua Waites (JIC)

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) is one of the most important and widely used techniques in molecular biology, allowing the selective amplification of specific DNA sequences from small amounts of template. By repeatedly cycling through phases of DNA denaturation, primer annealing and extension, PCR can generate millions of copies of a defined DNA fragment within a short period of time. This technique underpins many molecular workflows, including genetic analysis, diagnostics, forensics and cloning. It is also a key step in confirming successful assembly of DNA constructs in gene editing experiments.

In this session, participants will learn how to set up and run a PCR reaction, understand the purpose of each component in the reaction mix, and optimise thermal cycling conditions for different targets. Practical emphasis will be placed on accurate pipetting, correct reagent preparation, and use of the thermocycler. By the end of this session, participants will understand the theory behind PCR amplification and gain hands-on experience in preparing and analysing their own PCR reactions. Following this practical, participants will run their amplified products using agarose gel electrophoresis.

Protocol:

The basic steps

PCR goes through thermal cycling, repeating three main steps:

1. **Denaturation (94–98°C):** The double-stranded DNA melts into single strands.
2. **Annealing (50–65°C):** Short DNA primers bind to their complementary sequences on the single-stranded DNA.
 - » Annealing temperature can be calculated based on online tools such as NEB Tm Calculator: <https://tmcalculator.neb.com/>
 - » Typically, it is best to use the Tm calculator of the company who produced your Taq polymerase
3. **Extension (72°C):** Taq DNA polymerase extends the primers, synthesizing new DNA strands by adding nucleotides.

These steps are repeated typically 25–35 cycles to exponentially amplify the DNA target.

Components of a PCR reaction

1. **Template DNA** – the DNA sample containing the target region.
2. **Primers** (forward and reverse) – short DNA sequences flanking the target region.
3. **dNTPs** – deoxynucleotide triphosphates (A, T, G, C).
4. **Taq DNA Polymerase** – thermostable enzyme that synthesizes DNA.
5. **PCR buffer** – maintains the pH and salt conditions.
6. **MgCl₂** – a cofactor for Taq polymerase, recommended final concentration is 1.5 mM (may already be present in the buffer)
7. **Nuclease-free water** – to make up the total volume.

Example of a standard PCR reaction (20 μL volume)

Component	Volume (μL)	Final concentration
Template DNA	1	Variable
5× PCR Buffer	4	1X
dNTPs (10 mM each)	0.4	200 μM each
Forward Primer (10 μM)	0.5	0.25 μM
Reverse Primer (10 μM)	0.5	0.25 μM
Taq Polymerase (5 U/ μL)	0.1	0.025 U/ μL
Nuclease-free Water	13.5	-
Total	20 μL	-

Mix components in a 0.2 mL PCR tube, briefly spin down using a microfuge, and place in thermocycler, before finally starting a programme like the one below.

Example of a thermocycler program

Step	Temperature	Time	Cycles
Initial Denature	95°C	2 min	1
Denature	95°C	30 sec	25–35
Annealing	55–60°C	30 sec	
Extension	72°C	1 min/kb	
Final Extension	72°C	5–10 min	1
Hold	4°C		

Agarose gel electrophoresis

Trainers: Dr Anne Edwards, Dr Nikolai Adamski, Dr Joshua Waites (JIC)

Agarose gel electrophoresis is a fundamental technique used to separate DNA fragments by size, allowing researchers to visualise and verify results of molecular experiments or for genotyping. It works because DNA is negatively charged and will migrate through an agarose gel matrix towards the positive electrode when an electric current is applied. Smaller DNA fragments move more easily through the porous gel, travelling further than larger ones. After electrophoresis, the gel is stained with a fluorescent dye (such as SYBR Safe) which binds to nucleic acids, enabling visualisation of DNA bands under UV or blue light illumination.

In this session, participants will learn how to prepare and pour an agarose gel, load DNA samples alongside a molecular weight ladder, and run the gel under appropriate voltage conditions. The practical will demonstrate how to interpret band patterns to confirm successful PCR DNA amplification, and later we will see how to use this method to confirm correct cloning. Proper handling, safety precautions, and waste disposal procedures will also be covered, ensuring participants gain both the technical skills and theoretical understanding required to confidently perform DNA gel electrophoresis in the lab.

Protocol:

Equipment

- Microwave-safe conical flask (choose size based on desired gel size)
- Weighing scale
- Microwave
- Gel casting tray + casting dams
- Well combs
- Running tank
- P10 pipette
- P20 or P200 pipette
- Voltage source / power supply
- UV transilluminator + camera

Materials and reagents

- DNA or PCR product to test
- Agarose powder
- 1X TAE or TBE buffer
- 6X loading buffer (if not already in DNA or PCR product)
- GelRed DNA stain (10,000X stock)
- Pre-prepared DNA ladder (e.g. NEB 1 Kb ladder)
- P10 pipette tips
- P20 pipette tips

Procedure

- Wear appropriate personal protective equipment: lab coat, safety glasses and gloves. Observe local safety rules.
- Agarose gels are commonly used in concentrations of 0.7% to 2% depending on the size of the linear bands needed to be separated.
 - The greater the agarose percent, the slower the DNA fragments will travel through the matrix, so smaller DNA fragments can be separated on gels with greater agarose percentages (such as 2%):

Agarose (%)	Range of separation (kbp)
0.7	0.8-10
1	0.5-7
1.2	0.4-6
1.5	0.2-3
2.0	0.1-2

1. For 50 mL of 1% gel, dissolve 0.5 g of agarose in 50 mL 1x TBE buffer in the microwave. Ensure the lid is not on the bottle to allow steam to safely escape. Use short (<3 min) heating times at 50% power or less and swirl to mix. Be aware that the mixture may superheat with explosive results when agitated. Let solution cool for 1 min before removing from microwave. Use face shield and heat-resistant gloves.
2. Cool down to approx. 50°C (hand warm). While the gel is cooling, prepare the gel casting tray by taping both ends or inserting the casting dams.
3. Once sufficiently cooled, add 5 µL of GelRed DNA stain (the final GelRed concentration is therefore 1X) and mix well. Pour the gel to about 7.5mm thick or just below the well depth on the comb.
4. Allow to stand for 15-30 min for polymerisation.
5. If DNA samples / PCR products do not already contain loading dye, add 1 µL of DNA loading buffer per every 5 µL DNA solution.
6. Remove combs plus the tape or dams from the gel and place it (still on the casting tray) in the chamber with enough running buffer (1xTBE) to cover the gel completely.
7. Load samples (e.g. 15 µL) and DNA ladder (e.g. 5 µL) by pipette.
8. Run at 100V until the bottom blue band is close to the bottom of the gel. Ensure the correct power cables are connected to the cathode and anode.
9. Visualise on a DNA UV transilluminator and capture images if facilities allow. Ensure the use of a UV blocking visor to protect eyes if necessary.

Gels should be dried and discarded according to the local rules.

Integration of genomics to accelerate genetic gains in wheat

Trainer: Dr Susanne Dreisigacker (CIMMYT)

Wheat is an essential component of global trade and food security, providing around 20 % of protein and calories consumed worldwide. The demand for wheat is projected to continue to grow over the coming decades, particularly in the developing world to feed an increasing population, and with wheat being a preferred food, continuing to account for a substantial share of human energy needs in 2050. The CIMMYT Global Wheat Program is one of the most important public sources of high yielding, nutritious, disease- and climate-resilient wheat varieties for Africa, Asia, and Latin America, and is therefore a central pillar for more resilient agri-food systems in these countries. To keep up with the pressing future demands of wheat production and to adapt to changing environmental factors, wheat breeders at CIMMYT are constantly turning to new and emerging technologies and breeding strategies. Advanced genetics and genomics technologies are one of these and are progressively deployed and related operating processes are optimized.

Additional genome editing techniques

Led by: Dr Joshua Waites (JIC)

In this session we will explore some additional genome editing techniques of increasing interest to plant scientists. These include base editing, as well as the more adaptable prime editing, which aim to introduce predetermined single nucleotide polymorphisms and insertions, as opposed to the random short INDELS of canonical CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing. While the application of prime editing in plants is rising rapidly, a remaining challenge in plant genome engineering is the precise insertion of larger (>1 kbp) sequences. We will therefore also examine the potential for another method - homology-directed repair (HDR) - to overcome this barrier, as well its limitations.

15:30 - 16:30 Tuesday | Session 31 | Technical skills

Analysing Sanger sequencing data with Benchling

Trainer: Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)

Sanger sequencing is a popular method for analysing the sequence and/or variants of a short region of DNA/RNA. In this session we shall overview the process of why we use Sanger sequencing, and how to prepare samples for analysis. Furthermore we will detail how the sequencing works on the molecular level, followed by a tutorial on Benchling in which we will learn how to align and interpret the sequence data files produced, including the chromatograms and basepair confidence scores. By the end of this session you should be able to understand the function of Sanger sequencing, as well as how to understand and analyze the sequence results generated.

9:00 - 11:00 Wednesday | Session 32 | Laboratory practical

Assembly of wheat gene editing construct through Golden Gate cloning

Trainers: Dr Joshua Waites, Dr Nikolai Adamski, Dr Anne Edwards (JIC)

Golden Gate is a powerful method for assembling DNA constructs in a single reaction by combining digestion and ligation steps into just one tube. In this session we will use Golden Gate cloning to insert a guide RNA sequence into the wheat CRISPR/Cas9 vector pJD633 using the Type IIS restriction enzyme AarI. These Type IIS enzymes cut outside of their recognition sites, generating custom overhangs that allow seamless, directional assembly of DNA fragments, an approach that has become the foundation for modern modular cloning systems such as MoClo (<https://www.addgene.org/cloning/moclo/>).

In this session, we will first prepare complementary forward and reverse oligos representing the 20-nt guide RNA target sequence. These oligos are mixed and duplexed to create a short double-stranded DNA fragment with sticky ends compatible with AarI digested pJD633. This duplex is then combined with the pJD633 plasmid, AarI and T4 DNA ligase in a single digestion-ligation (diglig / one-pot) reaction, where multiple cycles of digestion at 37°C and ligation at 16°C ensure efficient and scarless cloning. We will then use the resulting plasmid for *E. coli* transformation and later checking steps to ensure correct Golden Gate cloning. This plasmid will then be able to be used for wheat transformation and gene editing.

Protocol:

Equipment:

- Micropipettes + tips
- Mini centrifuge
- Thermocycler (PCR machine)
- Ice bucket

Reagents and materials:

- Guide RNA oligo Forward (100 µM)
- Guide RNA oligo Reverse (100 µM)
- pJD633 plasmid
- Sterile water
- T4 ligase buffer
- T4 ligase
- AarI restriction enzyme
- 0.2 mL PCR tubes
- 1.7 mL Eppendorf tubes (for making working primer stocks)

First make up an oligo mix and duplex these

We ordered our guide RNAs as two single stranded oligos which complementary pair. Our first step is to mix these together and make sure they pair correctly in a dedicated oligo duplexing reaction.

1. Separately, make up a 10 µM working stock of the forward and reverse guide RNA oligos
2. Add the following to a 0.2 mL PCR tube:

Reagent	Volume
Guide RNA forward oligo (10 uM)	1 µL
Guide RNA reverse oligo (10 uM)	1 µL
T4 ligase buffer	1 µL
Water	7 µL

3. Put this oligo mix (2 µM) into a thermocycler for the following steps:

Temperature	Time	Ramp conditions
37°C	1 hour	6°C/second ramp to 37°C
95°C	10 min	6°C/second ramp to 95°C
25°C	Hold step	0.1°C/second ramp to 25°C

Set up the digestion-ligation (diglig) reaction

Once the oligo duplex mix has finished, you can go ahead and set up the digestion-ligation reaction. This does the digestion and ligation steps in a single reaction and a single tube, which is what GoldenGate cloning is great at. Firstly, the digestion reaction will digest the pJD633 plasmid at the AarI site, creating two sticky ends which are compatible with the guide RNA oligo duplex sequence we created in the previous step.

1. Set up the reaction mix as follows in a 0.2 mL PCR tube:

Reagent	Volume
pJD633 plasmid	Add 600 ng (calculate volume based on concentration of the plasmid)
Guide RNA oligo duplex (2 uM)	1 µL
T4 ligase buffer	1 µL
AarI restriction enzyme	0.5 µL
T4 ligase	0.5 µL
Water	Add up to a 10 µL total reaction volume

2. Put this into a thermocycler with the following steps:

Number of cycles	Temperature	Time
20 cycles of:	37°C	5 min
	16°C	5 min
1 cycle of:	37°C	20 min
	80°C	10 min
	4°C	Hold step

3. After this is done, you should have 10 µL of your diglig product, which will hopefully be a wheat gene editing CRISPR/Cas9 vector that will target TaGW2!

Feeding the future: genome editing as a catalyst for agricultural transformation in sub-Saharan Africa

Speaker: Prof. Valentine Otang Ntui (AGC, UM6P)

Feeding the growing population of Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) amidst climate change, declining soil fertility, and emerging pests and diseases remains a major challenge. Genome editing offers a transformative solution to these constraints by enabling precise, efficient, and cost-effective improvement of crops with desirable agronomic and nutritional traits. This technology allows for the rapid development of drought-tolerant, pest-resistant, and nutrient-enriched crop varieties tailored to local environments and farmer needs. Beyond enhancing productivity, genome editing contributes directly to achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) related to zero hunger, good health, and responsible consumption. However, realizing its full potential in SSA requires supportive policies, infrastructure, capacity building, and public awareness to address ethical and regulatory concerns. By integrating science, innovation, and inclusive governance, genome editing can serve as a powerful catalyst for agricultural transformation, food security, and economic resilience across the region.

13:15 - 16:30 Wednesday | Session 33 | Laboratory practical

E. coli transformation

Trainers: Dr Joshua Waites, Dr Anne Edwards, Dr Nikolai Adamski (JIC)

E. coli are often described as the workhorse of molecular biology, serving as an essential tool for propagating and maintaining recombinant DNA constructs. In this session, we will transform *E. coli* of the strain DH5-Alpha (which is one of the most common lab strains) with the plasmid DNA that we obtained from the previous Golden Gate reaction. That plasmid is our guide RNA sequence targeting TaGW2, inserted into the wheat CRISPR/Cas9 vector pJD633. The aim of this transformation is to introduce the newly assembled plasmid into bacterial cells so it can be replicated, selected and later isolated for sequence verification and downstream use (wheat transformation and then gene editing).

This protocol will guide participants through the transformation process using a chemically competent *E. coli* strain and the heat shock method. This covers key considerations such as the importance of recovery time for antibiotic resistance expression, handling cells gently to maintain viability, and plating multiple volumes to ensure well-isolated colonies. By the end of this session, participants will understand not only how to perform an *E. coli* transformation, but also the biological principles that make this step a cornerstone of molecular cloning workflows.

Protocol:

Equipment

- Ice bucket
- Waterbath at 42°C + timer
- 37°C shaking incubator at 200-220 rpm
- Microcentrifuge
- Micropipettes + tips
- Sterile spreader or disposable L-shaped spreader
- Laminar flow hood or a Bunsen burner / ethanol lamp

Reagents and materials

- *E. coli* cell aliquot of 50 µL kept at -80°C
- Plasmid/ligation product from transformation
- SOC media or liquid LB
- LB agar plates containing Kanamycin (Kan50)

Method

1. Allow the DH5a cell aliquot of 50 μ L to thaw on ice for 10-15 minutes
2. Add the plasmid/ligation product for transformation, for pJD633 use 5 μ l
 - » 1-5 μ L of DNA depending on size of plasmid
3. Put back on ice and incubate for 10 minutes
4. Heat shock at 42°C for 45 seconds
5. Immediately put back on ice and incubate for 5 minutes
6. Add 800 μ L of SOC media or LB
7. Put in shaker for ~2 hours
 - » Can be 1-2 hours. 1 hour is usually best with ampicillin resistance but 2 hours works best for kanamycin resistance
 - » This is to allow the bacteria to recover slightly before we select them on an antibiotic
8. Pellet the culture gently: in a centrifuge at RCF ~1,000 to 2,000 xg for 5 minutes
9. Resuspend in ~200 μ L of the supernatant (by removing 650 μ L of supernatant)
 - » Gently disturb the the pellet by mixing with a P1000 pipette
10. Plate two separate amounts on Kan50 plates. 40 μ L on one plate and 120 μ L on another
 - » By plating two separate amounts you reduce the risk of ending up with a "lawn" of colonies covering the plate if the *E. coli* transformation was too successful. The plate at 40 μ L will likely still have isolated single colonies that are able to be picked even if the 120 μ L plate is covered in colonies.

Group activity: Designing scientific posters and presentations

Trainer: Matthew Shackleton-Chavez (University of East Anglia)

This session focuses on two activities for learning and discussing scientific posters and presentations. This session will allow you to examine and critique examples of posters and presentations, to avoid common mistakes and create better content for your future careers. The first segment is on posters in which we shall teach good poster design, followed by small group activities in which you will examine and rate a selection of pre-prepared posters based on the poster's merits, followed by open floor discussion between groups for which the best and worst attributes will be discussed. The second segment shall first introduce the concepts of good presentation design and delivery, followed by small group activities examining example poster slides, followed by open floor discussion.

9:00 - 12:30 Thursday | Session 36 | Laboratory practical

Colony PCR to confirm correct Golden Gate assembly and *E. coli* transformation

Trainers: Dr Anne Edwards, Dr Joshua Waites, Dr Nikolai Adamski (JIC)

Colony PCR is a simple and quick method for screening bacterial colonies for the presence of a correctly assembled DNA construct. After performing the *E. coli* transformation in the previous session, this technique will allow us to identify which colonies contain the desired plasmid; those with a successfully inserted guide RNA sequence following Golden Gate cloning into pJD633.

In this session, participants will learn how to pick individual colonies and lyse these to serve directly as PCR templates. We will use primers that only amplify off plasmids with a correctly assembled plasmid, which contains our desired TaGW2 target sequence within the pJD633 plasmid. By doing so we can distinguish "positive colonies" from empty or misassembled colonies based on the size of the PCR product. This approach saves time and resources by allowing only those positive colonies to be cultured for further plasmid extraction and sequencing.

By the end of this session, participants will understand the principles of colony PCR and how to interpret gel electrophoresis results to identify correctly assembled CRISPR/Cas9 vectors for downstream applications.

Protocol:

Equipment

- P200, P10, and P2 pipettes
- Universal tubes (30 mL) or similar
- Laminar flow cabinet or bunsen burner
- Thermocycler (PCR machine)
- 37 °C shaking incubator
- Gel electrophoresis equipment (see previous protocol)

Consumables

- Sterile tips or toothpicks
- 0.2 mL PCR tubes

- LB liquid media
- Antibiotic stock solution - 50 mg/mL kanamycin in our case
- Nuclease-free water
- PCR primer working stocks (forward and reverse) (10 µM)
- GoTaq reaction buffer (green, 5X)
- GoTaq G2 DNA polymerase
- dNTPs (10 mM)
- Nuclease-free water

Method

1. Set up inside a laminar flow cabinet or on a bench with a lit Bunsen to prevent contamination of your transformation plates.
 - » Prepare three PCR tubes with 100 µL nuclease-free water
 - » Prepare three universal tubes with 5 mL LB liquid medium plus appropriate antibiotics to maintain the clone (50 µg/mL kanamycin for pJD633)
 - » Retrieve your overnight plate of transformed cells from the 37 °C incubator
2. Use a sterile micropipette tip or a sterile toothpick to transfer cells from three colonies to the three PCR tubes. Vortex briefly to resuspend.
3. Transfer each tip/toothpick to one of the LB-containing universal tubes.
4. Heat the PCR tube containing the cells at 95 °C for 10 minutes to lyse the bacteria.
5. Set up a PCR master mix for five samples.
 - » In this case setting up a master mix won't save loads of time as we are only testing three colonies plus two controls, but it would if you had to conduct the same PCR test on many samples.
 - » The master mix should comprise the following multiplied by the number of samples:

Reagent	Stock conc.	Volume (µL)	Final conc.
GoTaq reaction buffer* (green)	5X	4	1X
dNTPs	10 mM	0.4	0.2 mM
Forward primer	10 µM	0.5	0.25 µM
Reverse primer	10 µM	0.5	0.25 µM
GoTaq G2 DNA polymerase	5 U/µL	0.1	0.025 U/µL
Nuclease-free water	NA	12.50	NA
Total per sample	NA	18	NA

*Note: If using GoTaq G2 Flexi, you need to add your own MgCl₂. This is needed because Mg²⁺ is an essential cofactor for DNA polymerases. Recommended final concentration is 1.5 mM.

6. Aliquot 18 µL master mix into three different PCR tubes, then add 2 µL of a bacterial lysate to each tube (ensure you record which clone went into which tube).
 - » We also need a negative and a positive control.
 - » For the negative control, aliquot 18 µL master mix and 2 µL nuclease-free water.

- » For the positive control, aliquot 18 µL master mix and 2 µL of the provided positive control plasmid solution.

7. Amplify target DNA with appropriate thermocycling conditions, e.g.

Step	Temperature (°C)	Time (s)	Cycles
Initial denaturation	94	60	1
Denaturation	94	30	30 - 40
Annealing	45-68	30	
Extension	72	60 s / kbp	
Final extension	72	300	
Hold	4	NA	NA

8. Analyse products by agarose gel electrophoresis.
 - » Note that the GoTaq reaction buffer we used already contains a loading dye.
9. Retain the liquid cultures containing positive clones and grow overnight at 37 °C in a shaking incubator. 5 mL is the appropriate volume for subsequent miniprep of the target plasmid. (Larger volumes would be needed to acquire larger quantities of plasmid using a midi- or maxiprep kit.)

13:15 - 16:30 Thursday | Session 37 | Technical skills

GetGenome presents: don't clone alone, ensure your vectors are verified

Speaker: Dr James Canham and Dr Joe Win (GetGenome)

GetGenome (<http://www.getgenome.net/>) is a non-profit organisation dedicated to democratising access to genomics. To date, we have supported more than 150 researchers across a network of 100 institutes in over 20 countries. Among our initiatives is **GGPlasmidSeq**, a free plasmid sequencing service designed to promote best practice in molecular biology (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16785942>). In this session, we will build on practical exercises with a combined theoretical and hands-on workshop focused on inspecting and quality controlling plasmid sequences. Participants will learn how to identify common errors that only whole-plasmid sequencing can reveal, and understand why these checks are critical for reliable downstream research. As sequencing technologies become increasingly accessible, we will also describe how researchers can engage with GGPlasmidSeq to validate their own plasmids, strengthening reproducibility and confidence in their work.

Plasmid purification

Trainers: Dr Nikolai Adamski, Dr Joshua Waites, Dr Anne Edwards (JIC)

During their growth overnight, the *E. coli* cells have replicated our plasmid over 10,000-fold, acting as a biological factory for us. We now need to purify these plasmids for either further assembly, Agrobacterium-mediated plant transformation, or Sanger sequencing. To do this, we will use a common commercial kit (QIAGEN QIAprep Spin Miniprep Kit) that allows for fast and easy extraction of small quantities (<20 µg) of plasmid DNA.

Consumables and equipment:

Consumables

- Overnight *E. coli* cultures
- Qiaprep kit reagents and tubes
- 1000 µL tips
- 200 µL tips
- 10 µL tips
- 2 ml microcentrifuge tubes
- 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes
- DNase-free water

Equipment

- P1000 pipette
- P200 pipette
- Table-top centrifuge
- Tip waste (biological)
- Tip waste (non-hazardous)
- Waste bottle (biological / bacterial)

Protocol:

1. When using a new kit do the following:
 - » Optional: Add LyseBlue reagent to Buffer P1 at a ratio of 1 to 1000. 1 vial of LyseBlue reagent per bottle of Buffer P1.
 - » Add the provided RNase A solution to Buffer P1, mix, and store in the fridge at 2–8°C. 1 vial of RNase A solution per bottle of Buffer P1.
 - » Add ethanol (96–100%) to Buffer PE before use (see bottle label for volume).
2. Pellet 1–5 mL bacterial overnight culture by centrifugation at >8000 rpm (6800 x g) for 3 min at room temperature (15–25°C)
 - » Grow a 5 ml culture and pellet 4 mL for miniprep. This leaves ~1000 µL for making a glycerol stock or inoculating a fresh culture (e.g. for midiprep).
 - » Decant the culture into a 2 ml microcentrifuge tube. Make sure you do not overfill the tube so that it can be closed without spillage. Centrifuge the tube, decant the supernatant into an appropriate waste container, then fill the tube again from the same culture. This way, you pellet 4 ml into a single 2 ml tube.
3. Resuspend pelleted bacterial cells in 250 µL Buffer P1.
 - » Add the buffer, close the 2 ml tube, and rub the base of the tube across the back of a tube rack to quickly resuspend the cells.
4. Add 250 µL Buffer P2 and mix thoroughly by inverting the tube 4–6 times until the solution becomes clear (keep inverting until solution is clear; do not vortex!). Do not allow the lysis reaction to proceed for more than 5 min. If using LyseBlue reagent, the solution will turn blue.
5. Add 350 µL Buffer N3 and mix immediately and thoroughly by inverting the tube 4–6 times. If using LyseBlue reagent, the solution will turn colourless.

6. Centrifuge for 10 min at 13,000 rpm (~17,900 x g) in a table-top microcentrifuge.
7. Apply the supernatant from step 6 to the QIAprep spin column by decanting or pipetting. Centrifuge for 30–60 s and discard the flow-through.
 - » Depending on the amount of cell debris, it is advisable to stick a 10 µL pipette tip onto a 1000 µL pipette tip to avoid sucking up excess debris.
8. Optional: Wash the QIAprep spin column by adding 0.5 mL Buffer PB. Centrifuge for 30–60 s and discard the flow-through
 - » Note: This step is only required when using endA+ strains or other bacteria strains with high nuclease activity or carbohydrate content.
9. Wash the QIAprep spin column by adding 750 µL Buffer PE. Centrifuge for 30–60 s and discard the flow-through.
10. Centrifuge the empty column for 1 min to remove residual wash buffer.
11. Place the QIAprep column in a clean 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube. To elute DNA, add 50 µL Buffer EB (10 mM Tris·Cl, pH 8.5) or DNase-free water to the centre of the QIAprep spin column, let stand for 1 min, and centrifuge for 1 min.

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Sample preparation for plasmid Sanger sequencing

Trainers: Dr Nikolai Adamski, Dr Joshua Waites, Dr Anne Edwards (JIC)

Sanger sequencing is still a fast and easy method to verify the sequence of a DNA sample. Having prepared plasmid DNA from the overnight cultures of our assembled construct, we can proceed to check the sequence of the various clones.

If you have many clones, it is more cost-effective to first run a diagnostic restriction enzyme digest; then only select clones for Sanger sequencing that show the expected restriction band pattern. If sequencing a large plasmid, for example a fully assembled Level 2 construct, it is cheaper and more accurate to use whole-plasmid sequencing (usually nanopore sequencing) offered by a commercial supplier.

This protocol is for Sanger sequencing within an in-house facility. The protocol is the same whether you use individual microcentrifuge tubes, tube strips, or 96-well plates. If you use an external sequencing provider, follow their guidelines.

Consumables and equipment:

Consumables

- DNA (plasmid / genomic / PCR amplicon)
- Sequencing primer
- BigDye Terminator v3.1 (reagent and buffer)
- 10 µL tips
- 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes
- DNase-free water

Equipment

- P10 pipette
- PCR machine (thermocycler)
- Table-top centrifuge
- Nanodrop spectrophotometer
- Tip waste (non-hazardous)

Protocol:

1. Measure DNA concentration of the samples to be sequenced.
 - » Measure each sample using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer or similar device. Make sure to use the same solution for your "blank" measurements as was used to elute the DNA sample. For example, if your sample was eluted in 10 mM Tris·Cl, pH 8.5, then use that same solution for the blank measurement.
2. Recommended DNA amounts are:
 - » 100 to 200 ng of standard cloning plasmids (pBluescript, pGemT, etc.)
 - » 500 ng of binary vector
 - » 50 ng of PCR product of 1 kb length; calculate accordingly for products of different lengths
3. Set up reactions in 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes following the recipe below:
 - » **x** µL DNA (see above for recommended amounts)
 - » 1.5 µL 5x BigDye sequencing buffer
 - » 3.5 µL primer (1 µM)
 - » 1 µL BigDye reagent
 - » 4-**x** µL dH2O
 - » Total reaction volume is 10 µL
4. Run PCR using the following program:

Temperature	Time	Cycle
96°C	2 min	1
96°C	10 sec	25
55°C (or appropriate annealing temperature)	30 sec	
60°C	4 min	
15°C	1 min	1
4°C	Hold	N/A

5. Submit samples to your in-house sequencing facility.

Group activity: revision and reflection

Trainers: Kes Maio & Eleanor Penny (JIC)

This session will provide space for reflection on the course content across AfriPlantSci 2025. Together, we will go through some questions on what we learned, the things we found most important, and the things we would like to learn more about in the future. This offers an opportunity to record the skills learned during the workshop, which can later be added to your CV in order to enhance future employability. This will also be a space to revise topics and to ask any remaining questions to on-hand trainers prior to leaving the workshop.

Worksheet

What are the three main things you would like to remember from this workshop?

What is a technique/topic you have learned about that you feel you would now be able to teach to a colleague?

What is a topic discussed during the course that you are keen to learn more about?

What are some key skills you have learned or developed that can now be added to your CV?

Notes

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